

Techniques of Sinus Lift - Review Article

Shilpi¹
Sanjeev Kumar Salaria²
Chander Shekhar Joshi³
Mona Dagar⁴
Rashmi Shiwach⁵
Aashi Bhardwaj⁶

PG Student¹
Department of Periodontology & Implantology
DJ College of Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar

Professor & Head²
Department of Periodontology & Implantology
DJ College of Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar

Professor³
Department of Periodontology & Implantology
DJ College of Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar

Professor⁴
Department of Periodontology & Implantology
DJ College of Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar

Reader⁵
Department of Periodontology & Implantology
DJ College of Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar

Senior Lecturer⁶
Department of Periodontology & Implantology
DJ College of Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar

Submitted 15 April 2026
Accepted 16 April 2026
Published 12 June 2026

Access this article online Website : www.updent.in	QR Code Barcode
DOI	

Abstract

This review article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of sinus lift procedures as a predictable solution for implant placement in the atrophic posterior maxilla. Following tooth loss, progressive alveolar bone resorption and maxillary sinus pneumatization reduce the available bone height, posing a significant challenge for implant therapy. Sinus augmentation techniques, including direct (lateral window) and indirect (crestal) approaches, have been developed to overcome these limitations.

The article discusses the anatomy of the maxillary sinus, diagnostic modalities, classification systems, and various surgical techniques, along with modifications such as balloon sinus lift. It also highlights different graft materials, including autogenous, allogenic, and alloplastic options, emphasizing their clinical applications and advantages. Potential intraoperative and postoperative complications, including Schneiderian membrane perforation and infection, are reviewed with their management strategies.

Furthermore, the role of alternative approaches such as angulated and short implants is evaluated, although their long-term predictability remains uncertain. Evidence suggests that sinus lift procedures provide reliable outcomes with improved implant survival rates. The importance of proper patient selection, surgical expertise, and postoperative care is emphasized.

In conclusion, sinus lift procedures remain a well established and effective method for increasing residual alveolar bone height and ensuring successful implant rehabilitation in compromised maxillary conditions.

Keywords - Sinus lift, Maxillary Sinus Augmentation, Sinus floor Elevation, Lateral Window Technique, Crestal (osteotome) Sinus Lift, Indirect Sinus Lift.

Introduction

Dental implants have significantly advanced the rehabilitation of the edentulous posterior maxilla by enabling predictable fixed prosthetic solutions. However, this region often exhibits reduced alveolar bone height along with close proximity to the maxillary sinus, posing challenges for implant placement.¹ Following extraction of teeth in the posterior maxilla, progressive alveolar bone resorption occurs along with inferior expansion of the maxillary sinus into the residual ridge, a phenomenon known as sinus pneumatization. This results in reduced bone volume and a thin sinus floor, making implant placement challenging. To address this limitation, the sinus lift procedure was developed, first proposed by Tatum in 1977 and later described in detail by Boyne and James in 1980.^{2,4} This review explores the different

clinical presentations, classifications, surgical techniques, and postoperative protocols related to sinus lift procedures. It is based on an extensive literature search from multiple databases, emphasizing clinical trials, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses, to support evidence based decision making in planning sinus augmentation for dental implants.

Anatomy of Maxillary Sinus

The maxillary sinus, also known as the antrum of Highmore, is the largest of the paranasal sinuses. It is a pyramidal, air-filled cavity located within the body of the maxilla. The base of the sinus faces medially

How to Cite This Article : Shilpi et al. -

toward the nasal cavity, while the apex extends laterally toward the zygomatic bone [Figure 1]. The sinus floor lies in close proximity to the roots of the posterior maxillary teeth, particularly the molars, and may occasionally extend to the premolar region. Drainage of the maxillary sinus occurs through an opening known as the ostium, which empties into the middle meatus of the nasal cavity.⁵

Two radiographic methods that are in the use for sinus evaluation are:

1. Panoramic Radiograph
2. Computerized Tomography Scans

Fig 1 : Maxillary Sinus Anatomy

Fig 2 : Sub-antral Classification

Although Water's view (occipitomeatal view) is commonly used for initial assessment of the maxillary sinus, cyst like lesions are more clearly visualized on orthopantomogram (OPG) and computed tomography (CT) scans. A key advantage of OPG and CT over Water's view is their ability to accurately evaluate the residual alveolar bone height between the sinus floor and alveolar crest, which is essential for implant planning. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is highly sensitive for detecting pathological changes in the sinus mucosa and serves as a valuable adjunct for obtaining additional diagnostic information.

Anatomic Considerations

In general, three anatomical approaches are commonly used to access the maxillary sinus:

1. The superior approach, corresponding to the classic Caldwell–Luc entry, located just anterior to the zygomatic buttress.
2. A mid-level approach, positioned between the alveolar crest and the zygomatic buttress.
3. An inferior approach, located along the anterior maxillary wall at the level of the existing alveolar ridge.

This classification helps guide the selection of the most appropriate surgical access based on anatomical and clinical considerations.⁶

Subantral Classification and Treatment Options

Misch classified treatment options based on the available bone height between the floor of the maxillary sinus and the crest of the residual alveolar ridge at the intended implant site. [Figure 2 and Table 1]

Table 1: Subantral classification and management				
Classification (subantral-SA)	Bone height and width	Management	Graft	Implant placement
SA-1	12 mm height (adequate) from crest to floor of sinus Bone width if inadequate, bone augmentation or osteoplassty recommended	Conventional implant placement Ridge splitting to increase bone width	Inter positional graft to increase width	Implant left to heal for 4-8 months
SA-2	10-12 mm remaining bone	Indirect sinus lift procedure with osteotome	Green stick fracture of sinus floor and lifted along with graft	Implant placed and loading after 6-8 months If apical bone formation could not be revealed in radiograph wait another 2 months and follow progressive loading protocol
SA-3	Atleast 5 mm of vertical bone	Direct sinus lift by lateral window technique	Autogenous or alloplast graft in sinus lifted space	Implant delayed for 2-4 months
SA-4	<5 mm of residual alveolar bone	Same as SA-3		Implant delayed for 6-10 months (6)

Surgical approach for Sinus Augmentation

The management of severe maxillary atrophy may involve a Le Fort I osteotomy, which is considered an extensive surgical procedure. In this technique, the maxilla is mobilized and repositioned via an intraoral approach, allowing placement of a large volume of autogenous cancellous bone graft along the sinus floor and lateral walls. Dental implants may also be placed simultaneously during the procedure. However, its use is limited by factors such as the need for general anesthesia, patient age, and underlying systemic health conditions.⁴ The atrophic posterior maxilla can be managed using either indirect (crestal) or direct (lateral window) sinus augmentation techniques.

Indirect Sinus Augmentation Technique

Cases with a residual alveolar bone height of approximately 6–8 mm are generally managed using the indirect (crestal) sinus augmentation technique. Under local anesthesia, the implant site is prepared by initiating osteotomy with a pilot drill to establish the correct angulation, followed by sequential drills of increasing diameter to match the implant size. Care is taken to maintain the drilling depth about 1–2 mm short of the sinus floor. Sinus elevation is then achieved using osteotomes of increasing diameter, which gently fracture and elevate the sinus floor, allowing for implant placement.

The sinus floor is carefully elevated by controlled fracture of the sinus floor, ensuring separation from the Schneiderian membrane without causing perforation. This is achieved using a surgical mallet with gentle, controlled force. When indicated, autogenous graft material is introduced into the osteotomy site. The graft is gradually advanced apically using instruments of increasing diameter, facilitating elevation of the sinus membrane and condensation of graft material beneath the elevated sinus floor.

Alternatively, the sinus floor can be elevated using a greenstick fracture technique with flat-top osteotomes, which allow simultaneous displacement of the sinus floor along with the graft material. Modified osteotomes are specifically designed to minimize the risk of membrane perforation during elevation. Following adequate lift and graft placement, the implant can be placed immediately into the prepared site. The surgical wound is then closed using 3–0 Vicryl sutures. Postoperatively, patients are prescribed antibiotics, anti-inflammatory medications, and nasal decongestants for five days. Clinical and radiographic follow-up is performed periodically to monitor healing and implant success.⁷ [Figure 3 and 4]

Fig 3 : Indirect Sinus Lift Technique

Fig 4 : Modified Osteotomes

Direct Sinus Augmentation Technique (Residual Alveolar Bone(RAB)5mm or below)

Residual alveolar bone (RAB) height of ≤ 5 mm is generally considered an indication for the lateral window sinus augmentation technique. Autogenous bone grafts are commonly harvested from intraoral donor sites such as the external oblique ridge of the mandible or the parasymphysis region. The harvested bone is processed into fine particulate form using a bone mill.

Following administration of adequate local anesthesia, a crestal incision is made over the residual ridge at the appropriate site, along with vertical releasing curvilinear incisions extending into the vestibule. Full thickness mucoperiosteal flaps are elevated both buccally and palatally to expose the anterolateral wall of the maxillary sinus. Care should be taken to identify and preserve the infraorbital nerve when present in the surgical field.

The size and location of the osteotomy are determined based on clinical and radiographic assessment, as well as the extent of the edentulous span. A lateral access anotomy is created by outlining the window using a round bur. The osteotomy is typically rectangular with rounded corners. Controlled rotary instrumentation with copious irrigation is continued using light, brush like strokes until a bluish hue becomes visible, indicating close proximity to the Schneiderian membrane. [Figure 5]

The bony window is then carefully mobilized using gentle tapping or the “postage stamp” technique. The sinus membrane is meticulously elevated from the inner surface of the sinus wall without perforation, allowing access for subsequent graft placement.

The previously harvested graft material is then placed into the sinus cavity and gently packed to achieve adequate volume and stability. Implant placement may be performed simultaneously using a surgical stent to ensure proper faciolingual and mesiodistal positioning.

Osteotomy preparation is carried out using a standard reduction gear handpiece with a physiodispenser, allowing copious saline irrigation to minimize heat generation. Drilling is performed at a speed of 800–1000 rpm. Sequential drilling is completed according to the planned implant dimensions, following which the implant is inserted into the prepared site using a torque-controlled wrench.

Wound closure and postoperative management, including suturing and medication protocol, are similar to those employed in the indirect sinus lift technique.

In cases with minimal or no residual alveolar bone height, a two stage approach is preferred. In this protocol, graft material is placed following sinus elevation and allowed to heal for approximately 6–8 months. After adequate bone regeneration, a second-stage surgery is performed for implant placement. The implant is then allowed an additional healing period of around 6 months before prosthetic loading is carried out.

Fig 5 : Direct Sinus Lift

Variation of Surgical Techniques

Apart from the conventional direct and indirect sinus lift techniques, several modified approaches have been developed to enhance safety and clinical outcomes. Modified osteotomes with rounded tips are designed to avoid fracturing the sinus floor; instead, they facilitate gentle bone compaction, resulting in gradual elevation of the sinus floor along with the graft material.

Another advanced technique is the balloon sinus lift, in which an elastic catheter is inserted into the osteotomy site and gradually inflated with saline. This controlled expansion elevates the Schneiderian membrane uniformly, thereby significantly reducing the risk of membrane perforation.⁸

Grafts used for Sinus Graft Surgery

The use of alloplastic grafting materials has increased significantly in recent years. These materials can be utilized either alone or in combination with autogenous bone, demineralized bone, blood, or other biologic adjuncts. A major advantage of alloplastic grafts is the elimination of donor site morbidity associated with autogenous bone harvesting.

Commonly used alloplastic materials include hydroxyapatite, calcium phosphate ceramics, beta-tricalcium phosphate, calcium sulfate (gypsum), bioactive glass, and polymethyl methacrylate.

Allogenic Materials

Allogenic bone is derived from living and cadaver donors.

Allogenic materials are of two different types:

1. Mineralized
2. Demineralized

Demineralized bone grafts are widely used due to their osteoinductive potential. These materials contain bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs), which stimulate adjacent undifferentiated mesenchymal cells to differentiate into osteoblasts, thereby promoting new bone formation. Demineralized bone grafts are typically obtained from tissue banks and can be used alone or in combination with autogenous bone to increase graft volume and enhance clinical outcomes. Bone morphogenetic proteins were first identified in the 1960s by Marshall Urist, who demonstrated their ability to induce ectopic bone formation when implanted into animal tissues. These proteins are isolated using advanced techniques such as amino acid sequencing and recombinant DNA technology. Among the various BMPs identified, BMP-2 and BMP-7 have been the most extensively studied for clinical applications. Recombinant human BMP-2 (rhBMP-2) has been shown to be an effective alternative to autogenous bone grafts, such as those harvested from the iliac crest, with comparable clinical and radiographic outcomes, while eliminating donor site morbidity.⁸

Autogenous Bone

Autogenous bone is considered the gold standard among all bone graft materials due to its osteogenic potential, excellent biocompatibility, and absence of disease transmission risk. Common donor sites for maxillary sinus augmentation include extraoral locations such as the posterior iliac crest and tibia, as well as intraoral sites like the maxillary tuberosity, mandibular ramus, and mandibular symphysis.

A systematic review by Ali et al. (2015) evaluated the role of platelet rich fibrin (PRF) in sinus augmentation procedures. The authors reported that PRF, when used as a sole grafting material, demonstrated promising outcomes. Additionally, PRF was found to enhance and accelerate the maturation of demineralized freeze dried bone allograft (DFDBA). It is also considered an effective, simple, and minimally invasive option for covering the sinus membrane or the lateral osteotomy window.⁹

Complications

The complications of sinus graft procedures are usually rare if promptly diagnosed. Postoperative infections rates are reported as 2% and 5.6% with no distinction between true sinus and sinus graft infections.

Intraoperative complications of sinus lift procedure

Apart from swelling, hematoma, infection which would occur postoperatively, an important intraoperative complication in direct sinus lift procedures is as follows:

- Perforation of Schneiderian membrane
- Displacement of dental implant into sinus
- Presence of septal partition in the sinus cavity.

Perforation of Schneiderian Membrane

Perforation of the Schneiderian membrane is one of the most common complications encountered during sinus lift procedures, as it can compromise the stability and survival of the bone graft. Management of such perforations is performed intraoperatively and primarily depends on the size and location of the defect. Once a perforation occurs, excessive manipulation or pressure should be avoided to prevent further

enlargement. Minor perforations can often be managed by gently folding the membrane onto itself or by sealing the defect using a small collagen tape or a bioabsorbable membrane. In contrast, larger perforations require more meticulous management, including careful suturing of the membrane followed by the application of fibrin adhesive. A bioabsorbable membrane is then placed over the repaired site. Importantly, the sinus walls are not covered in such cases to preserve the vascular supply essential for graft integration.¹⁰

Vlassis and Fugazzotto proposed a classification system for sinus membrane perforations along with corresponding treatment strategies based on defect severity.¹¹

Additionally, the “Loma Linda pouch” technique has been introduced as an effective method for managing perforations during sinus grafting procedures. In this approach, a collagen membrane is first positioned over the perforation and adapted to the internal surface of the maxillary sinus. It is then folded along the lateral window to create a pouch that contains and stabilizes the graft material. This technique minimizes the risk of graft migration into the sinus cavity and enhances graft isolation. Following placement, buccal and palatal flaps are sutured to achieve closure. Although promising, this technique requires further clinical and histological validation.¹²

Displacement of Implant into Maxillary Sinus

Causes of Implant Displacement into Maxillary Sinus

- Implant placement in posterior maxilla without adequate sinus augmentation
- Inadequate knowledge of maxillary sinus anatomy
- Unnoticed perforation of the sinus floor during osteotomy
- Excessive force during implant insertion (e.g., tapping in internal sinus lift)

Management / Retrieval Methods

- Transalveolar approach: Removal through osteotomy or extraction site using suction (if accessible)
- Caldwell-Luc operation: Surgical access via anterior sinus wall for retrieval
- Endoscopic sinus surgery: Minimally invasive transnasal retrieval with lower morbidity

Modern sinus endoscopy, first described by Walter Messerklinger in 1960 and later introduced in the United States in 1985, has become a minimally invasive approach for the retrieval of displaced implants from the maxillary sinus. This technique minimizes tissue trauma while preserving mucociliary function. The procedure involves placing a deep Partsch incision in the anterior fornix, followed by elevation of a mucoperiosteal flap. A small bony window is then created in the canine fossa to allow access without excessive bone removal. The endoscope is carefully introduced into the sinus to localize the displaced implant, which is subsequently retrieved under direct visualization using curved instruments. Typically, a 3–4 mm, 0° Hopkins endoscope, such as those provided by Karl Storz, along with a xenon light source, is used to ensure optimal visualization during the procedure.¹³

Maxillary Sinus Septa

Maxillary sinus septa were first described by Arthur Underwood in 1910.¹⁴ These bony partitions are most

commonly located in the region between the second premolar and first molar. Their presence can complicate sinus lift procedures by increasing the risk of membrane perforation and limiting surgical access. In cases where septa create a complete or partial partition within the sinus, management typically involves the creation of multiple lateral windows to safely elevate the Schneiderian membrane and bypass the septal obstruction.¹⁵

Postoperative Complications

Infection

Postoperative infection after sinus augmentation most commonly develops in the grafted area beneath the sinus membrane rather than within the sinus cavity itself. In some cases, the infection may extend into the sinus and manifest as pan-sinusitis. Recommendations by Tiziano Testori are based on expert consensus from multiple specialties.

Common postoperative symptoms include swelling, bruising, mild to moderate pain, and minor nasal bleeding, which typically resolve within three weeks. Preventive and postoperative care protocols are mainly derived from clinical experience.

If symptoms persist beyond three weeks and are associated with pus discharge, fistula formation, nasal or throat discharge, flap dehiscence, or suppuration, an underlying infection should be suspected. Such cases require multidisciplinary management. Surgical intervention, including Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery, along with removal of the graft and implant via an intraoral approach, may be necessary. Microbiological testing is recommended after initiating antibiotic therapy to guide further treatment.¹⁰

Recommendations

Appropriate Clinical Recommendations

A thorough evaluation of the patient’s medical history and appropriate case selection are essential, ensuring the presence of a healthy maxillary sinus. Comprehensive diagnostic investigations should be performed, along with the elimination of existing endodontic and periodontal pathologies prior to surgery. In patients with a history of heavy smoking (exceeding 15 cigarettes per day), implementation of a structured smoking cessation protocol is strongly advised. Optimal oral hygiene must be achieved, with full-mouth plaque and bleeding scores maintained below 15%. Strict adherence to sterilization protocols is mandatory to minimize the risk of infection. Additionally, a well structured follow-up regimen should be established, consisting of weekly reviews during the first postoperative month, followed by monthly evaluations for the subsequent three months.¹⁶

Postoperative Instructions

- Apply firm pressure by biting on a gauze pack over the surgical site for at least 20 minutes; ideally maintain for 3–4 hours.
- Strictly follow all prescribed medications and postoperative instructions.
- Mild bleeding from the mouth or nose may occur; report immediately if excessive or persistent.
- Small white particles in the mouth or nose may appear due

- to escape of graft material.
- Facial swelling on the operated side is common and typically subsides within 2 weeks.
- Bruising (ecchymosis) over the cheeks, neck, or shoulder region may occur and resolves gradually.
- Maintain a liquid diet for the first 48 hours, followed by a soft diet for 2 weeks.
- Keep the head in an upright position as much as possible.
- Rinse gently with 0.12% chlorhexidine mouthwash 3–4 times daily.
- Take adequate rest to promote healing.
- Prophylactic antibiotics and post operative medications has been prescribed. [Table 2]
- Calcium supplementation may be advised to support bone healing.¹⁷

Table 2: Antibiotic prophylaxis and postoperative medications

Condition	Prophylaxis	Postoperative therapy
Patient not allergic to penicillin	Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid 1 g twice a day (BID) per OS One hour before surgery	Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid 1 g thrice a day (TID) per OS For 7 days
Patient allergic to penicillin	Clarithromycin 250 mg BID + metronidazole 500 TID per OS starting 24 h before surgery	Clarithromycin 250 mg BID + metronidazole 500 TID per OS for 7 days

BID: Twice daily, TID: Three times daily, OS: Oral stat

Restrictions

Smoking should be avoided for at least two weeks following surgery, with a preference for abstinence up to six weeks to ensure optimal healing. Alcohol consumption should be restricted for the first 48 hours. Patients are advised to avoid activities that increase pressure in the surgical area, such as blowing the nose, forceful sneezing, bending forward, using straws, spitting, or vigorous rinsing. Additionally, playing wind instruments and the use of removable dentures or night guards should be avoided during the initial healing period.^{17,18}

Discussion

In cases of an atrophic maxilla, implant placement is often not feasible without invasive procedures such as bone augmentation, sinus lift, or both. Although these procedures are generally successful, complications such as Schneiderian membrane perforation, epistaxis, postoperative pain, and swelling may occur; however, these are not considered significant factors affecting implant success rates.¹⁹ Additionally, inadequate bone availability may lead to increased patient anxiety, fear of additional surgical interventions, and higher treatment costs.²⁰

Angulated (tilted) implants have been investigated as a potential alternative to sinus lift procedures. Studies have shown that crestal bone loss associated with tilted implants is comparable to or even less than that observed with axial implants.²¹ However, the placement of a single angulated implant for replacing a single missing tooth is generally not recommended due to the risk of off-axis loading from fixed prostheses.²² A meta-analysis has further demonstrated no significant difference in success rates between tilted and axial implants.²³ These findings support the use of tilted implants as a viable alternative with high success rates similar to conventional implants. Nevertheless, a systematic review by Asawa et al. highlighted that this technique is highly technique-sensitive, particularly beneficial in patients with resorbed ridges, and requires further long-term studies to assess outcomes related to load distribution, marginal bone loss, and prosthetic

survival. Despite these concerns, this approach is increasingly utilized in clinical practice with favorable outcomes.²⁴

Smoking is considered a relative contraindication for implant therapy and remains a controversial factor influencing implant success, particularly following sinus lift procedures. A retrospective study evaluating the impact of smoking on implants placed in grafted maxillary sinuses reported a significantly higher success rate in nonsmokers (82.7%) compared to smokers (65.3%) over a mean follow-up period of 42 months, with no direct correlation between implant failure and the number of cigarettes consumed.¹⁷

Comparative studies on direct and indirect sinus lift procedures have shown increased residual alveolar bone height following direct sinus lift; however, these findings were not statistically significant.⁷ Furthermore, a Cochrane systematic review by Esposito et al. (2010) suggested that short implants (approximately 5 mm) may be successful in cases with residual bone height of 4–6 mm, although their long-term predictability remains uncertain. The crestal approach was recommended for bone heights between 3–6 mm to facilitate implant placement.²⁵ Another systematic review by Saraperaz Martinez (2015) concluded that sinus lift procedures are a reliable and effective method for achieving vertical bone gain in the range of 5–9 mm.²⁶

Conclusion

The long-term success of sinus grafting procedures is primarily assessed based on implant survival rates. Implants placed in conjunction with sinus lift grafts have demonstrated more favorable outcomes compared to those placed without grafting. Evidence from the literature suggests that the success of angulated or short implants remains less predictable, thereby supporting sinus lift procedures as a reliable method for increasing residual alveolar bone height, typically in the range of 5–9 mm.

Both direct and indirect sinus lift techniques require comprehensive knowledge of maxillary sinus anatomy, meticulous preoperative assessment and diagnosis, precise surgical

execution, and consistent postoperative follow-up with regular recall visits to ensure optimal outcomes.

Financial Support and Sponsorship

Nil.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Tatum H Jr. Maxillary and sinus implant reconstructions. *Dent Clin North Am* 1986;30:207-29.
2. Riben C, Thor A. The Maxillary Sinus Membrane Elevation Procedure: Augmentation of Bone around Dental Implants without Grafts-A Review of a Surgical Technique. *Int J Dent* 2012; 2012: 105483.
3. Boyne PJ, James RA. Grafting of the maxillary sinus floor with autologous marrow and bone. *J Oral Surg.* 1980; 38: 613-6.
4. Carl E. Misch. *Contemporary Implant Dentistry*. 3rd ed.. St. Louis: Mosby; 2008.
5. Tiwana PS, Kushner GM, Haug RH. Maxillary Sinus Augmentation. *Dent Clin North Am* 2006; 50: 409-24.
6. Jensen, Ole T. *The Sinus Bone Graft*. Ch. 5. Third edition, Quintessence publishing, USA; 1999.
7. Balaji SM. Direct v/s Indirect Sinus Lift in Maxillary Dental Implants. *Ann Maxillofac Surg* 2013; 3:148-53.
8. Garg A. DMD. Bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) for some lift. *Dental Implantol Update* 2010; 21: 24-9.
9. Ali S, Bakry SA, Abd-Elhakam H. Platelet Rich Fibrin in Maxillary Sinus Augmentation: A Systematic Review. *J Oral Implantol* 2015; 41:746-53.
10. Testori T, Drago L, Wallace SS, Capelli M, Galli F, Zuffetti F, et al. Prevention and treatment of postoperative infections after sinus elevation surgery: clinical consensus and recommendations. *Int J Dent* 2012; 2012: 365809.
11. Vlassis JM, Fugazzotto PA. A classification system for sinus membrane perforations during augmentation procedures with options for repair. *J Periodontol* 1999; 70: 692-9. Devameena, et al.: Sinus lift procedures in dental implants 186 *Indian Journal of Dental Sciences* | Volume 12 | Issue 3 | July-September 2020
12. Proussaefs P, Lozada J. The "Loma Linda pouch": A technique for repairing the perforated sinus membrane. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent* 2003; 23: 593-7.
13. Altan Varol DD, Turker N. DDS: Endoscopic retrieval of dental implants from the maxillary sinus. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants* 2006;21; 801-4.
14. Underwood AS. An Inquiry into the Anatomy and Pathology of the Maxillary Sinus. *J Anat Physiol* 1910; 44: 354-69.
15. Kim MJ, Jung UW, Kim CS, Kim KD, Choi SH, Kim CK, et al. Maxillary sinus septa; Prevalance, height, location and Morphology: A reformatted computed tomography scan analysis. *J Periodontol* 2006; 77; 903-8.
16. Al-Dajani M. Recent Trends in Sinus Lift Surgery and Their Clinical Implications. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res* 2016; 18: 204-12.
17. Stern A, Green J. Sinus lift procedures: An Overview of Current Techniques. *Dent Clin North Am* 2012; 56: 219-33.
18. Kan JY, Rungcharassaeng K, Lozada JL, Goodacre CJ. Effects of smoking on implant success in grafted maxillary sinuses. *J Prosthet Dent* 1999; 82: 307-11.
19. Taschieri S, Del Fabbro M, Tsesis I, Corbella S. Maxillary Sinus in relation to Modern Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. *Int J Dent* 2012; 2012: 391012.
20. Bortoluzzi MC, Manfro R, Fabris V, Cecconello R, Derech ED. Comparative study of immediately inserted dental implants in sinus lift: 24 months of follow-up. *Ann Maxillofac Surg* 2014; 4: 30-3.
21. Rosén A, Gynther G. Implant treatment without bone grafting in edentulous severely resorbed maxillas: A long-term follow-up study. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 2007; 65: 1010-6.
22. O'Mahony A, Bowles Q, Woolsey G, Robinson SJ, Spencer P. Stress distribution in the single unit osseointegrated dental implant: Finite element analyses of axial and off axial loading. *Implant Dent* 2000; 9: 207-18.
23. Ata-Ali J, Peñarrocha-Oltra D, Candel-Marti E, Peñarrocha-Diago M. Oral rehabilitation with tilted dental implants: Ametaanalysis. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal* 2012; 17: e582-7.
24. Asawa N, Bulbule N, Kakade D, Shah R. Angulated implants: an alternative to bone augmentation and sinus lift procedure: Systematic review. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2015; 9: ZE10-3.
25. Esposito M, Grusovin MG, Rees J, Karasoulos D, Felice P, Alissa R, et al. Effect of sinus lift procedures for dental rehabilitation: A cochrane systematic review. *Eur J Oral Implantol* 2010; 3;7-26.
26. Pérez-Martínez S, Martorell-Calatayud L, Peñarrocha-Oltra D, García-Mira B, Peñarrocha-Diago M. Indirect sinus lift without bone graft material: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Exp Dent* 2015; 7: e316-9.